

Development of solid dispersions of b-lapachone in PEG and PVP by solvent evaporation method

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ABSTRACT

b-lapachone (blap) has shown potential use in various medical applications. However, its poor solubility has limited its systemic administration and clinical applications. The aim of this work is to develop solid dispersions of blap using poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG 6000) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP K30) as hydrophilic polymers and evaluate the dissolution rate in aqueous medium. Solid dispersions were prepared by solvent evaporation method using different weight ratios of blap and hydrophilic polymer (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3). Characterization performed by differential scanning calorimetry, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, and scanning electron microscopy showed that blap was molecularly dispersed within the polymer matrix. The *in vitro* dissolution tests showed an enhancement in the dissolution profile of blap as solid dispersions prepared in both PVP and PEG, although the former showed better results. The drug:polymer ratio influenced blap dissolution rate, as higher amounts of hydrophilic polymer led to enhanced drug dissolution. Thus, this study demonstrated that solid dispersions of blap in PVP offers an effective way to overcome the poor dissolution of blap.

KEYWORDS: b-Lapachone; solid dispersion; PEG 6000; PVP K30; dissolution rate

Introduction

b-lapachone (blap) (Figure 1) is a naphthoquinone derived from lapachol that has shown potential use in various medical applications due to its antiviral, anti-parasitic, anti-tumor, and anti-inflammatory properties [1–5]. However, its poor aqueous solubility (0.038 mg mL⁻¹) limits its systemic administration and clinical applications *in vivo*. To overcome this limitation, several studies have been carried out in order to investigate techniques that can enhance the solubility and dissolution rate of blap, such as the use of inclusion complexes with β -cyclodextrin [6,7], nano/microparticles [8,9], hydrogels [10,11], and liposomes [12].

Another alternative to enhance the dissolution rate of poorly soluble drugs is the preparation of solid dispersions (SDs), which consists of dispersing the insoluble drug in a highly hydrophilic matrix, where the drug can be molecularly dispersed or in the amorphous state [13–15]. Although SDs have been prepared by kneading, wet milling, wet mixing, electrospinning and microwaves irradiation, the solvent evaporation is still the most used method as the drug is usually dispersed within the hydrophilic matrix at the molecular level [14,15].

In fact, increase in the dissolution rate of carbamazepine [16], piroxicam [17], loratadine [18], efavirenz [19], and atorvastatin/ezetimibe [20] has been successfully achieved through the use of SD technique. The main advantages of this method are the particle size reduction, an increase in wettability and porosity of the drug, as well as the conversion of the crystalline state to a more soluble amorphous state [21,22].

Due to their strong hydrophilic character, synthetic polymers such as poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) have been extensively used as hydrophilic matrices for SD preparation [23–25].

For the best of our knowledge, the use of SD method to increase the dissolution of blap has not been investigated so far. Thus, the present study aims to develop SDs of blap in PEG and in PVP by using the solvent evaporation method and characterize the obtained complexes. In addition, the dissolution profiles of blap alone and as SDs were investigated in aqueous medium. Finally, the dissolution data were fitted into mathematical models with the purpose of better describing the mechanism of release/dissolution of blap from the polymer matrices.

Materials and methods

Materials

blap (3,4-dihydro-2,2-dimethyl-2 H-naphthol[1,2-b]pyran-5,6-dione) was supplied by Laboratório de Síntese de Compostos Bioativos (UFRPE, Brazil). blap was obtained by acid cyclization of lapachol, which was extracted from the bark of the lapacho tree (*Tabebuia avellanedae*). PEG (6000), PVP (K30), and absolute ethanol were obtained from Synth (São Paulo, Brazil). Sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO, USA). All other materials were of analytical grade.

Figure 1. The chemical structure of b-lapachone.

Preparation of the SDs

SDs of blap were prepared using PEG 6000 and PVP K30 as hydrophilic polymer matrices through different drug:polymer ratios (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3, w:w). The SDs were prepared by the solvent evaporation method, where proper amounts of blap and each hydrophilic polymer were dissolved in ethanol (20 ml). After complete dissolution, the solvent was evaporated overnight at room temperature. The SDs were then grinded using mortar and pestle, passed through a 250- μ m sieve and finally stored in desiccator until use.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC measurements were performed using 4 mg of each SD in an aluminum pan and submitted to a temperature range of 25–525 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ using a DSC apparatus (TA Instruments, SDTQ600, New Castle, USA) under nitrogen atmosphere at a flow rate of 50 ml min⁻¹.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD patterns of the SDs and individual components were obtained using a X-ray diffractometer (Mini Flex II, Rigaku, Massachusetts, USA) fitted with Cu K α radiation at 30 mA and 45 kV, using diffraction angles (2 θ) between 5° and 30°.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectra were obtained using a device equipped with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan, IRAffinity-1). Thirty-two scans were performed for each spectrum within the range of 4000 to 700 cm⁻¹ using a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The morphology of the SDs and individual components was examined using a scanning electron microscope (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan, SSX-550 Superscan). The samples were deposited onto double-sided carbon tapes and covered with a fine film of gold to obtain a good conductivity of the electron beam.

Dissolution study

The *in vitro* dissolution study of blap was conducted in 450 ml of aqueous SLS solution 0.5% (w/v) under a stirring rate of 75 rpm (paddle apparatus) at 37 \pm 0.5 °C. The dissolution tests were performed in a Sotax AT7 (Basel, Switzerland) for blap alone as well as SDs containing an equivalent of 10 mg of the drug. Samples were collected (5 ml) at predetermined time points (5, 10, 20, 30, 45, and 90 min), filtered through a cellulose filter and analyzed by UV spectrophotometry at 257 nm. Equal volumes of SLS 0.5% were

replaced after each withdrawal. All experiments were carried out in triplicate.

Mathematical modeling of blap release

In order to understand the release mechanisms of blap from the PEG and PVP matrices, the dissolution data were fitted to Korsmeyer–Peppas and Weibull models [26,27].

In the Weibull model, the cumulative fraction of the drug in solution is considered as a function of time t , according to Equation (1):

$$\log^{1/2} - \ln \delta | - m \delta |^{1/4} b \log \delta t - T_i \delta - \log a \quad (1)$$

where, a defines the timescale of the process, T_i is the time interval before the release starts (zero in most cases), and b is a shape parameter that characterizes the exponential curve as follows: $b < 1$, first-order kinetics; $b > 1$, sigmoid (fast kinetics); and $b < 1$, satellite (slow kinetics) [27].

The mathematical model proposed by Korsmeyer and Peppas [28] exponentially correlates drug release with time, as described in Equation (2):

$$f_t \approx at^n \quad (2)$$

where, a is a constant associated with the structural and geometrical characteristics of the pharmaceutical formulation, n is the release exponent that indicates the mechanism of drug release, and f_t is the fractional drug release at time t (M_t/M_1 , where M_t is the amount of drug released at time t and M_1 is the amount of drug released at infinite time).

The models proposed by Korsmeyer and Peppas and Weibull were applied to the blap dissolution curves in order to characterize the mechanism of release of this drug from the SDs in PEG and in PVP. These curves can explain how the molecules are released from SDs systems, enabling determination of the values of k , n , b , and the linear correlation coefficient [29,30].

Results and discussion

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Although DSC has been used as a valuable tool for evaluating the formation of SDs, this technique has not been appropriate in cases where the drug has low melting point as well as when it is dispersed within the polymer matrix at very low concentration, such as those below 5% [31]. On the other hand, the lowest concentration of blap used in this current study was 25% (1:3) in respect to the hydrophilic polymer. In addition, the DSC curves for blap, hydrophilic polymers, and the SDs (Figure 2) show endothermic peaks at about 156 °C and 66 °C, which correspond to the melting point of blap and PEG, respectively [8,22]. PVP exhibited a broad endothermic peak in the range of 45–142 °C, which is attributed to the loss of water due to its extremely hygroscopic nature [18].

For blap/PEG SDs, the endothermic peak attributed to blap disappeared even at the 1:1 blap:PEG ratio, which might indicate that blap is molecularly dispersed within the PEG matrix. For blap/PVP SDs, the endothermic peak attributed to the drug is switched to about 143 °C and its intensity is markedly decreased at the 1:1 ratio. However, the peak attributed to blap completely disappeared when the amount of PVP increased (blap:PVP ratio of 1:3). The progressive decrease in the peak intensity of blap seems to be due to the increasing dissolution of the drug in the polymer matrix as the amount of PVP increases. The formation of SDs usually involves a reduction in the drug's crystallinity caused by

Figure 2. DSC curves of blap, PEG, PVP, and solid dispersions.

Figure 3. XRD patterns of blap, PEG, PVP, and solid dispersions.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra of blap, PEG, PVP, and solid dispersions.

possible chemical interaction between the drug molecules and the polymer [23]. In fact, SDs can form either eutectic mixtures (the components are not mixed at the molecular level) or solid

solutions (a molecular level mixing occurs) [13]. Therefore, it seems likely to assume that the solvent evaporation method enabled blap to form solid solutions with both PVP and PEG.

Figure 5. SEM image of blap, PEG, PVP, and solid dispersions.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The XRD patterns of blap, polymers, and SDs are shown in Figure 3. blap exhibits a sharp crystalline reflection at 9.5° and other secondary peaks at 13 , 15.4 , 19.5 , 22.8 , 24.7 , 25.4 , 26.4 , and 27° in the 2θ range [7]. PEG showed two characteristic strong 2θ peaks at 19.3° and 23.5° , while PVP shows no crystalline peak due to its amorphous nature [24].

On the other hand, the intensity of the XRD peaks related to blap and PEG were reduced in blap/PEG SDs, indicating a change in the crystalline form of these materials. However, the XRP pattern of blap/PVP SDs shows both a decrease and a broadening of in the intensity of the blap peaks when the amount of PVP was increased. Although both hydrophilic polymers were able to decrease the crystalline character of blap, the diffraction peaks due to blap have lower intensity in the SDs prepared with PVP than those prepared with PEG, which seems to indicate that the former polymer has a better ability to decrease the crystallinity of blap. Therefore, such low crystallinity might contribute to an enhancement in the dissolution profile of blap as amorphous or less crystalline materials are more readily soluble [32].

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectra for blap, polymers, and SDs are shown in Figure 4. blap displayed characteristic bands at 2978 cm^{-1}

(aromatic C-H stretch), 1694 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch), 1590 and 1567 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-C stretch), 1312 and 1115 cm^{-1} (C-O-C stretch) [7]. PEG showed a characteristic broad band at 3500 cm^{-1} (O-H stretch) as well as bands at 2882 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch) and 1095 cm^{-1} (C-O stretch) [32]. PVP exhibited bands at 2919 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch), 1648 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch), and 1282 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch). A broad band can also be seen at 3416 cm^{-1} (O-H group) associated with the presence of water [20].

The FTIR spectra for blap/PEG SDs show that the intensities of blap bands were reduced as the amount of PEG increased, indicating a possible intermolecular interaction between drug and polymer. This finding corroborates the XRD and DSC results, as they showed that increasing amounts of PEG led to enhanced molecular interaction with blap. Similar FTIR results was reported for SD of finasteride/PEG [32]. For blap/PVP SDs, the results were similar to the spectrum of blap, indicating that no significant molecular interaction occurred between the drug and the polymer matrix. This finding may also be related to a possible overlap of the bands attributed to both blap and PVP [18,33].

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The micrographs of blap, polymers, and SDs are shown in Figure 5. SEM images revealed that blap presents as an acicular crystalline structure [12], whereas PEG consists of large crystalline

Figure 6. Dissolution profiles of blap/PEG (A) and blap/PVP (B) with different weight ratios.

particles and PVP is composed of amorphous spherical particles [34]. The micrographs of all SDs revealed the presence of agglomerated particles of irregular sizes, where the original morphology of blap disappears, suggesting that this drug has been successfully dispersed within the polymeric matrix.

In SDs, the drug can be dispersed within the polymer matrix either at molecular level or as nanodispersions [35]. In this current study, the SEM micrographs of the SDs depicted in Figure 5 do not seem to show any nanoparticle that could be related to blap as the original particles of the latter have elongated shape. Moreover, the results of the DSC analysis (Figure 2) seem to indicate that homogeneous systems were obtained, where blap is in fact molecularly dispersed within the PVP and PEG matrices. However, techniques such as transmission electron microscopy and micro-Raman spectroscopy could be used to better describe the dispersion state of blap within the polymer matrices, as suggested by Karavas et al. [35].

Dissolution study

Despite the promising use of blap in many biomedical applications, its poor aqueous solubility imparts its clinical use. In fact, for a given drug to be well absorbed, it must be present in the form of an aqueous solution at the absorption site, which means that low aqueous solubility negatively affects the drug's bioavailability. Therefore, dissolution of poorly soluble drugs is one of the major

Table I. Values of the kinetic parameters obtained from the models applied to blap release curves.

Kinetic model fitting for the drug release data				
	blap/PEG 1:1	blap/PEG 1:2	blap/PEG 1:3	blap/PVP 1:1
Korsmeyer–Peppas				
<i>n</i>	0.250	0.264	0.245	0.164
<i>k</i> (min ⁻¹)	23.234	25.262	33.332	49.091
<i>R</i> ²	0.826	0.923	0.788	0.994
Weibull				
<i>a</i>	4.18	4.082	3.28	1.936
<i>b</i>	0.354	0.414	0.479	0.385
<i>R</i> ²	0.893	0.936	0.893	0.994

k: Release constant.

*R*²: Correlation coefficient.

n: Diffusion exponent.

a: Defines the time scale of the process.

b: Indicates the mechanism of transport of the drug in the system.

challenges during the development stage of new pharmaceutical formulations [36].

The dissolution profiles of blap alone and as SDs in PEG and in PVP are displayed in Figure 6. The blap/PEG SDs prepared with the 1:1 and 1:2 ratios did not provide an increase in the blap dissolution rate compared to that of the drug alone. However, an enhancement was observed for the SD prepared at the 1:3 ratio, where approximately 68% of blap was dissolved in 10 min against only 44% of that of the drug alone. These results suggest that higher amounts of PEG are required in order to prepare SDs that significantly increase blap's dissolution rate. A similar behavior was observed for the dissolution profiles of finasteride prepared as SD in PEG [37].

On the other hand, the blap/PVP SDs showed better dissolution profiles compared to that of blap/PEG, even at the lowest blap:PVP ratio. At 10 min of experiment, the dissolution of blap reached 72% (1:1) and 100% (1:2 and 1:3) when prepared as SDs in PVP. The SDs with 1:2 and 1:3 ratios exhibited almost identical dissolution profiles, revealing that an excess of the polymer does not favor an increase in the blap dissolution. Similar results were obtained for SDs of curcumin in PVP, prepared by spray drying technique at drug: polymer ratios of 1:7 and 1:10 [38]. Thus, it is likely to infer that PVP is a more effective carrier for blap than PEG. Studies carried out by other authors [23,24] corroborate this assertion.

The values of the kinetic parameters, obtained after applying the mathematical models for the *in vitro* dissolution/release data, are shown in Table I. Weibull model showed fitted *R*² values between 0.893 and 0.994. On the other hand, Korsmeyer–Peppas provided a better fitting model for the blap/PVP 1:1 formulation (*R*² ¼ 0.994; Figure 7). Other mathematical models were also applied to the data, such as those of zero order, first order, and Higuchi [27,29,39,40], but they did not show any advantage in fitting the experimental data. Samples prepared with 1:2 and 1:3 blap/PVP ratios were not analyzed due to the high dissolution rate of blap in these formulations (100% of blap dissolution in 10 min).

The values of the release exponent (*n*) below 0.43 and (*b*) at 0.75, extracted from the equations proposed by Korsmeyer–Peppas and Weibull, respectively, suggest that blap release is governed purely by classical Fickian diffusion, as shown in all the formulations [41]. In addition, Table I shows that the values found for the release constant, *k*, increased with increasing PEG's concentration in the SDs. The dispersions prepared with blap:PVP ratio of 1:1 presented a *k* value of 49.091 min⁻¹, which is two times bigger than that of 1:1 and 1:2 blap:PEG systems and 50% greater than that of 1:3 blap:PEG. Therefore, these results demonstrate that blap was released more rapidly from PVP matrix than that of PEG.

Figure 7. Results of the analyses of PEG and PVP with different weight ratios containing blap using the mathematical model of Peppas (A) and Weibull (B). - linear fit.

According to Karavas et al. [42], the higher molecular weight PVP must form a more viscous diffusion layer than PEG and this may impart a slower drug diffusion through the polymer layer. However, the fact that PVP formed SDs that are more amorphous than those of PEG (Figure 3) must have favored the dissolution process of blap in the aqueous medium. In fact, Karavas et al. [42] reported that the stronger the interaction between drug and PVP the lower is the crystallinity and size of the drug particles. Thus, it seems that the reduction in the blap's crystallinity played a more significant role in its dissolution.

Conclusion

SDs of blap in PEG and PVP were successfully prepared by the solvent evaporation method. The characterization results showed that blap is molecularly dispersed in both PEG and PVP matrixes, where the latter polymer was more efficient in increasing the dissolution rate of blap. Moreover, the drug:polymer ratio significantly influenced blap dissolution rate, as higher amounts of hydrophilic polymer led to enhanced drug dissolution.

Thus, the present study demonstrated that SDs of blap in PVP prepared by the solvent evaporation method showed to be an effective way to overcome problems related to the poor aqueous solubility of this drug, improving its dissolution rate and thereby serving as a good release system for use in pharmaceutical formulations.

Disclosure statement

The authors declare that this research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Funding

This research was financially supported by CAPES [02817/09-8] and PPGDITM.

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